

The speed-of-light measurement problem, the quantum gravity equation, and the unified description of the four fundamental forces

Li Yan¹⁾, Li Jia Xin²⁾

1) First author: Li Yan (ORCID ID:0009-0007-9009-140X)

2) Second author: Li Jia Xin (ORCID ID: 0009-0006-2037-3017)

Abstract: One cannot ignore the process of photon wave function collapse and re-formation in the measurement of the speed of light, based on which the truth can be found more in line with the reality of the universe. In the Viewing Angle principle, a unified description of the four fundamental forces can be deduced.

1. The process of photon wave function collapse and re-formation cannot be avoided in the process of light speed measurement

Reviewing the history of the measurement of the speed of light, we can know that physicists have used many ways to measure the speed of light, and there are mainly three kinds of results in the measurement, one is to measure the average speed of light in the interval; the second is to calculate the instantaneous speed of light by interferometric measurements of the wavelength and frequency of light; the third is to measure the isotropy (anisotropy) of the speed of light.

In the results of the measurement of the speed of light there are two properties that require special attention: one is the isotropy of the speed of light, in the speed of light isotropy of the test is the most typical of the Michelson-Morley Experiment, which ruled out the Ether said that the results of the modern test has shown that the anisotropy of the propagation of light is not greater than 10^{-17} level^①; one is the measurement of the wavelength and frequency of the light through the laser interferometric method, the instantaneous speed of light is obtained by calculating $c = \lambda f$ speed of light, obtaining the exact value of the speed of light and redefining the length meter^②.

As we all know, scientists have determined a conclusion through the measurement of the speed of light, "in all inertial systems, the speed of light propagation in the vacuum has the same value c ", based on this conclusion, Einstein established the theory of relativity.

Question: Is the speed of light really like that?

We know that in the process of measuring a quantum, the wave function of the quantum collapses, and the more precise the quantum momentum is in the measurement, the more imprecise the position becomes, which is the quantum indeterminate principle.

The same indeterminate principle is followed in the measurement of the speed of light.

A careful review of all the experiments on the measurement of the speed of light reveals a key issue that cannot be allowed to be avoided: when measuring the propagation speed of photons (or electromagnetic waves) relative to different speed reference systems, there is a process of collapse and re-formation the wavefunction of the photons (or electromagnetic waves), and this process cannot be avoided. So, we cannot simultaneously measure the propagation speed of a photon relative to two reference systems moving at different relative speeds. --Even, we have not measured it.

Based on this assertion, an explanation of the problem of the speed of light can be found, that is more in line with the objective facts.

(I) In neglecting the process of collapse and re-formation of the wave function, and via $c = \lambda f$, it must lead to the conclusion that the speed of light is constant.

Impose a "constant speed of light", i.e., "in all inertial systems, the propagation speed of light in vacuum has the same value c ", the relativity theory must be introduced to make the physical quantities of different frame of reference covariant.

Although the introduction of relativity theory can lead to correct conclusions most of the time, and can be used for calculations in many scenarios. But it differs from the objective world, and does not lead to a final correct solution.

(2) When the process of wave function collapse and re-formation is not ignored, this conclusion will be reached: The speed of light in a vacuum is different relative to the speed of propagation of "different frame of reference moving at different relative speeds".

During the measurement of the wavelength of a photon, when the head of the photon is detected by the moving measuring device, the measuring device continues to move, and by the time the tail of the photon has been measured, the measuring device has reached a new position. If the speed of the measuring device is not 0, the difference in position distance generated by this process is not equal to 0. This process is in essence the process of collapsing and regenerating the wave function of light. Without neglecting this process, photons propagate at different speeds relative to measuring devices moving at different speeds.

This process is the "relative spatial transition" of photons (or electromagnetic waves) in different frame of reference.

Corollary 1: Without neglecting the process of wave function collapse and re-formation, there is a "relative spatial transition" of photons (or electromagnetic waves) in different frame of reference, and after the measurement, the wave function of light follows the frame of reference of the observer, and the physical quantities of the different frame of reference is covariant.

"In all inertial systems, the speed of propagation of light in vacuum has the same value c ", a conclusion that needs to be supplemented with the key statement: "In all inertial systems, the speed of propagation of light in vacuum is unknown prior to the measurement, and can be assumed to have the same value in any single inertial system c . When an observer in an arbitrary frame of reference measures the propagation speed of a photon in another frame of reference of different speed, there is a process of collapse and re-formation of the wave function of that photon, and this photon after re-formation the wave function, will following with the observer's frame of reference, and propagation speed of c .--This is principle of constancy of light velocity after refinement.

(3) The propagation speed of a photon (electromagnetic wave) after it has been measured follows the frame of reference in which the observer is located, and the frame of reference includes the gravity frame of reference. When propagating between the interfaces of two gravitational fields, the photon undergoes the same relative spatial transitions, the wave function of photon collapse and re-formation, and the propagation of light in the same gravitational reference system appears isotropic.

This conclusion fully supports the conclusions of experiments on the isotropy (anisotropy) of light as measured by people.

If the "interface between the two gravitational fields" can be precisely determined, redoing the Michelson-Morley Experiment on this interface will yield different experimental results.

(4) "Relative spatial transitions" are the basis for the existence of most physical phenomena. In author's previous articles, have explained that "relative space" and "relative space transition" form the energy change of a moving system and constitute inertial mass, which is completely correct. The principle of gravity can be discovered based on relative space.

2. Principle of gravity, quantum gravity equation

2.1 Principle of Gravity

A and B are relatively stationary particles. In A and B, the internal electromagnetic waves propagate at the speed of light in their own space system, and there is no interaction between the two particles when only A exists in space, or when only B exists (Fig. 2.1.1).

When observing two particles A and B in space simultaneously, the two particles appear in each other's view angle changes. As shown in Fig. 2.1.2, A and B are separated by distance R. When observing B from the viewpoint of A, B is in a cone with A as its vertex. The larger the distance from B, the smaller the angle of the cone of view, and the smaller the distance, the larger the angle of the cone of view. On the surface of the sphere with A as the center and R as the radius, there are an infinite number of points, which are equivalent to point B. Then, A and B exist different relative spaces.

Take B at any position on the sphere. When A and B are observed together, relative to the relative space of particle A, the electromagnetic wave of particle B occurs a change in density during propagation.

In the direction tending toward A, the density of the electromagnetic waves of B relative to the relative space of A increased with time.

In the direction away from A, the density of the electromagnetic wave of B relative to the relative space of A decreases with time.

The electromagnetic wave of B relative to the relative space of A produces an overall difference in the tendency of A: the electromagnetic wave of B passes through the relative space belonging to A. Sparse away from A, dense near A. In the relative space of A, the electromagnetic waves of B show an overall tendency to converge toward A. This tendency creates an energy difference that tends toward A, leading to universal gravitation. When the perspectives of A and B are switched, the results remain unchanged.

This is the "Principle of Universal Gravitation" obtained under the new idea.

2.1 Quantum Gravity Equation

According to the "Principle of Universal Gravitation", the quantum gravity equation can be derived and the correctness of the principle can be further proved.

In this derivation, energy is used to explain the relevant equations.

As shown in Fig. 2.1.2, Fig. 2.2.1:

the distance between particles A and B is R, the mass of particle A is M, the energy is E, the mass of particle B is m, the energy is e, and the circular ratio is π . The relative spatial and energy of particle A and the Viewing Angle action on particle B form a sphere with radius R at particle B. The relative spatial action density (energy density) of particle A with respect to particle B at particle B is $\frac{E}{4\pi R^2}$.

According to the "principle of Universal Gravitation", the energy in particle B produces an energy difference in relative space with respect to particle A. As shown in Fig. 2.2.2, the energy propagating in all directions in particle B can be simplified, as shown in the figure, where only the part of the energy \overleftarrow{ab} directed toward A that can produce Universal Gravitation is considered, and its amount is $(1/2)^3$.

As shown in Fig. 2.2.3, the energy \overleftarrow{ab} amount $e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3$, part of the energy outside the angle θ is required to counteract the energy moving away from A in the \overleftarrow{ab} direction and is not accounted for in Equation. The energy within the angle θ , its amount is $e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \cdot \sin \theta$, which generates an energy trend towards A.

The trend of the energy generated is the energy $e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \cdot \sin \theta$, as it propagates in the direction of \overleftarrow{AB} , the increase in energy density due to compression in the cone of view of A, the "amount of

increase in energy density" is the energy difference Δe . And calculating Δe , according to the uncertainty principle, when calculating the change in the volume of B with relative to the volume of the cone of view with A, cannot according to the geometrical space of particle B, but it is necessary to consider all the energy propagating in B as propagating in the space relative to A. Then, relative to the space of particle A, the electromagnetic wave in particle B propagates in all directions, forming a sphere of electromagnetic wave with the center of mass of particle B as the sphere. Like the area $\frac{1}{4\pi R^2}$ of the relative space action at particle A relative to particle B, the volume of the cone of view of particle B relative to A changes by $\frac{1}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3}$. Then the energy difference in the space of action

$$\text{of particle B relative to A appears as } \Delta e = \frac{e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3}$$

The density of the relative spatial action of A (energy density) multiplied by the change in energy of B, that is the "energy that causes B to be attracted to A".

The following equations are formed when combined:

$$\frac{F}{g} c^2 = \frac{E}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 e \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3}$$

Organize the formula, Get the **Quantum Gravity Equation**:

$$F = \frac{M c^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 m c^2 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3} \cdot \frac{g}{c^2}$$

Simplified equation:

$$F = \frac{M m}{R^2} \cdot \frac{3g \sin \theta}{128\pi^2 c}$$

Where c is the speed of light and g is the acceleration of gravity. Among these, $\frac{3g \sin \theta}{128\pi^2 c}$ is a mathematical expression for the "universal gravitational constant." If particle A is considered as Earth, the physical meaning of the equation is the gravitational coefficient between the Earth's energy density per unit of space relative to a terrestrial object and the terrestrial object's energy per unit.

In this equation, the energy of the particle is calculated using Einstein's mass-energy equation $E = mc^2$, circumference π is 3.141592654, the speed of light c is 299,792,458 m/s, and the acceleration of gravity g is a constant at 9.807. The values of θ angle are shown in Fig. 2.2.3, when the θ angle is taken within 60° , the electromagnetic waves of B form an overall difference in energy, tending toward A. This energy forms the gravitational force. For energy outside angle θ , the gravitational force cancels out the repulsive force and is not accounted for in the equation.

Substituting the data into the equation gives $\frac{3g \sin 60}{128\pi^2 c}$, and the resulting value of the "universal gravitational constant" is $6.72736 \cdot 10^{-11}$, with an original value of $6.67387 \cdot 10^{-11}$ difference within 0.795%. The reason for this is that $F = \frac{M m}{R^2} \cdot \frac{3g \sin 60}{128\pi^2 c}$ it's quantum gravity, which is slightly greater than the actual measured gravity on the ground.

According to the calculation, angle θ can be taken as 59.22° , forming the Equation of Gravity $F = \frac{Mm}{R^2} \cdot \frac{3g \sin 59.22}{128\pi^2 c}$. After adjusting the θ angle, the calculations were perfectly consistent with those measured on the ground.

2.3 Quantum Gravity Equation is universal

The quantum gravity equation is universal and can be applied to various frames of reference. In the quantum gravity equation:

$$F = \frac{Mc^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 mc^2 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3} \cdot \frac{g}{c^2}$$

$\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3$ has the physical meaning of a sphere of electromagnetic waves centered on the center of mass of particle B, the speed of light is relative to either direction. The resulting gravitational force is independent of the state of motion of particle B. Regardless of the way particle B is moving and of how fast particle B is moving, if the relative space of action of particle A exists in the space in which the center of mass of B is located, this does not change the objective basis of the quantum gravity equation. In the formation of gravity, all the energy does not need to be converted between relative spaces, following the principle of invariance of the speed of light, and the "mass-energy increment" of the particles due to their relative motion has nothing to do with the formation of gravity.

2.4 Gravity equations for massive stars

The above quantum gravity equations, when applied to massive stars, need to consider the ratio of the gravitationally induced blue-shift and red-shift of the electromagnetic wave caused by the gravitational force of the massive star. In Fig. 2.2.2, if A is a massive star, the gravitational force of A will cause the energy of B to appear gravitational blueshift and gravitational redshift, and the same electromagnetic wave will have more energy in the blue-shifted direction than in the redshifted direction, so that the relative spatial action of the massive star on the object is greater, then the relative spatial action density of A at the point B is $\frac{Mc^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{f_b}{f_r}$, where f_b is the electromagnetic wave blueshift frequency, and f_r is the redshift frequency. The gravitational equations for massive stars are obtained: $F = \frac{Mc^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{f_b}{f_r} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 mc^2 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3} \cdot \frac{g}{c^2}$.

3. Viewing Angle Principle

In author's previous articles^③, defined the principle of gravity as relative spatial action, and the propagation of relative spatial action as the speed of light. This definition is correct, but it is still too cumbersome and requires a lot of content to explain relative space and relative space action. So, I simplify it to Viewing Angle Principle.

Viewing Angle exists in a certain structure, which can be called the Viewing Angle Structure. As in Figure 2.2.2, the viewing angle structure of gravity is a three-dimensional cone, which is the simplest viewing angle structure. Relative spatial action is equivalence with viewing angle and viewing angle structure. But viewing angle and viewing angle structure can be added to consciousness, and based on viewing angle and viewing angle structure, all things will be simpler and more direct, and even the existence of super-consciousness can be deduced.

Deeper principles can be discovered by thinking through Viewing Angle:

Corollary 2: Quantum Gravity (Universal Gravity) is created by particles viewing angle each other differently, and its magnitude depends on the total amount of waves in one particle, relative to the degree of imbalance in viewing angle structure, and viewing angle density of the other particle. The reverse is also true.

The existence and transmission of quantum gravity (Universal Gravity) requires only the objective existence of two particles relative to each other in space, which is determined by the transmission of viewing angle, the viewing angle structure and viewing angle density of the two particles, and does not require the transmission of the so-called "graviton" or any particle or any medium. The "graviton" does not exist.

The viewing angle density is determined by the total amount of waves each of the two particles contains and is an expression of the viewing angle structure.

Corollary 2 is a literal description of the gravitational equation and the underlying explanation of the principle of gravity.

In the study of gravity, the trend direction of energy in the viewing angle structure determines whether there is a gravitational or repulsive force between two particles. The denser the viewing angle structure, the greater the force. As the viewing angles get closer, the gravitational (repulsive) force is greater and grows inversely proportional to the square.

In author's previous articles, described that the electromagnetic waves in particles and the relative space of the particles have a "relative spatial action" on the external space. This relative action cannot exceed the speed of light. When a particle is created, its action on space propagates at the speed of light, and when this action propagates to other particles, the other particles begin to be subjected to the gravitational force of the particle. If the "spatial action" of the other particles already existed before the particle was created, at the location where the particle was created, the particle is immediately subject to the gravitational attraction of the other particles from the moment of its creation. Before the spatial action of the newly created particle propagates to the position of the other particles, the other particles will not be subject to the gravitational force of that particle. The gravitational forces are not always mutual, depending on the existence and propagation of the "spatial action".

So, the viewing angle structure also determines whether there is a force between the two, and the viewing angle structure is related to the structure of the particles, which gives rise to different fundamental forces.

Based on this concept, it can be known that the antigravitational force generated by the antigravitational model, is since its viewing angle structure is 90° different from that of ordinary particles in terms of direction, and gives rise to repulsive force with respect to any ordinary particles. Since the relationship between gravitational and antigravitational forces is the same as the relationship between electromagnetic attraction and repulsion listed later, antigravitational forces do not need to be distinguished as the fifth fundamental force.

Corollary 3: The concept of gravitational field is Inaccuracy. It is essentially the viewing angle and viewing angle structure of gravity, i.e., the relative action space of gravitational forces.

Based on Viewing Angle Principle, the gravitational equation can be further analyzed in depth.

When the speed of movement of particle B gradually increases, close to or even equal to the speed of light, it will not make particle B due to the change of mass and the occurrence of gravitational force infinitely increasing things. It was previously thought that the mass of a particle

moving at high speed would increase because of the increase in speed - a conclusion that can only be used in the transmission of forces "by contact or collision".

Corollary 4: For particles that only need viewing angle to act to transmit forces, the phenomenon of "mass increasing with velocity" does not exist. And the change in the relative mass of two particles moving at high speeds in relation to each other is unknown in the absence of contact or collision. -Because there is no God's perspective for either of the two particles.

Implicit in the Viewing Angle Principle is the notion that one must look at it from the viewing angle of a spectator to get the essential principle of gravity, which can be called God's perspective. God's perspective will be the best way to study physics in the future.

Observing from God's point of view, we can get several special forms of gravity and antigravity, and we can also get the special form of the relative space of particles connected with the space of the universe. It is these special forms that give our universe its supreme selflessness, infinite future and infinite possibilities, and the universe will not become a "collapse-explosion" cycle or a super black hole.

A brief description of rare manifestations of several forces below:

(1) Gravity is not always mutual

To explain this knowledge, which is far beyond common sense, let us have a super thought experiment. Of course, the following thought experiment is something one would not dare to think about, much less write about in any paper. But to explain that gravity is not always mutual, this experiment must be expounded.

Let us suppose that God, who is omnipotent, wanted one day to enjoy the beauty of the earth, and snapped his fingers, suspending the whole solar system for an instant, temporarily cancelling all the mutual forces of the planets, and cancelling all the light that had been emitted. All the planets could not see the other planets, and all could not see anyone else.

..... He took the earth away for a while - to show off the beauty of the earth in heaven.

Then God made the effects of the ringing finger disappear. The sun re-emitted its light, and the light began to propagation. A little time passed, and the sun's light reached the original location of the earth, and the sun did not see the earth, and the sun did not feel the earth's gravity.

Of course, the sun had so much to do that it didn't have time to think about where the Earth had gone, and the light continued to propagation.

After a few minutes, God put the earth back in its place.

After putting it back in place rings his finger! The second ringing of the fingers only pauses and does not cancel everything.

We can imagine what gravity looks like at this moment.

At this moment: the sun's rays are already shining at the Earth's location, and the Sun's relative spatial action is already present at the Earth's location.

The Earth is immediately affected by the gravitational force of the Sun.

However, the matter of the Earth being put back in its place is not yet seen or known by the Sun, because the Earth's action of space has not yet passed over to the Sun's side, and the Sun has not been affected by the Earth's gravitational force!

At this, we discover something that can't happen in regular physics: the forces of gravity are not always mutual.

Then the effects of the second ringing finger disappeared and all continued.

Eight minutes later, the Sun saw the light reflected from the Earth, and the Earth's relative

spatial action propagated to the Sun's position.

The Sun feels the Earth's gravity again. Then everything in the solar system returns to normal.

This thought experiment shows one thing: gravity is not always mutual, breaking through the "relativity of forces". This is the problem with mechanics, people have always assumed that forces are transmitted by matter or particles - this is not the case, we are all lost in the delusion and do not see the truth. If you go deeper and add an additional problem, it is that all mechanics needs to consider the speed of light, and needs to consider God's perspective.

Gravitational forces are not transmitted over distance in real time, they are not mutual at large scales, a feature that keeps the universe stable.

(2) Antigravity is not always mutual, forces are not always mutual

The latter thought experiment is even simpler, but the reasoning will be even deeper: at a certain point in time, an antigravitational device (hereinafter referred to as a "flying saucer") suddenly operates for half a second at an altitude of 300,000km above the Earth, and then shuts down.

During the "half-a-second of operation" of the flying disc, the flying disc was subjected to the anti-gravity force of the Earth.

The Earth began to be subjected to the counter-gravitational force of the flying disc about half a second after the disc shut down, and "continued to be so for half a second". During that two "half a second", the force on both was unidirectional.

During the half-a-second after the saucer was switched off and before the Earth received the counter-gravitational force from the saucer, there was no counter-gravitational force between the two.

Corollary 5: Forces are not always mutual.

Of course, people can explain all of this in terms of "space-time", and it is self-consistent in your pathetic theories. However, in the future, when people use quantum entanglement to fully realize "real-time" and "super-distance" transmission of information, and when people use flying saucers to realize superluminal travel, will also have to adhere to the fallacy of space-time? The so-called "space-time" has hindered the development of science for nearly a hundred years, and even if human life span is measured in 200 years, the radius of the light sphere we live in is only 200 light years. Do people not want to break through this pitiful cognitive barrier?

(3) Action of antigravity on close-range objects

Since both gravity and antigravity show the inverse square relationship of distance. Humans can cleverly design a flying saucer, so that the anti-gravity force can push the flying saucer to overcome the gravitational force to do ultra-high acceleration movement, at the same time, push the flying saucers "creatures and every particle of the object" to move with the same acceleration, to achieve super-light speed with ultra-high acceleration, and to achieve the real freedom of interstellar journey.

When the anti-gravity force is strong enough, it will form a strong enough repulsive force on objects in close-range, and will dramatically slow down any approaching matter (by applying a large reverse acceleration to the object), an "energy shield" would be formed with the flying saucer at its center, as fantasized in the film. Under the action of the anti-gravity force in a specific direction, the speed of the object that crashes into the flying saucer at high speed can be slowed down to zero, and then bounced back.

At the same time, the material molecules around the flying saucer will also be repulsive force, so that the flying saucer to isolate the air molecules and water molecules, supersonic movement in

the air will not appear sonic boom, in the ocean movement by the water resistance will also be very small impact. If the repulsive force generated by the flying saucer is strong enough to isolate all high-speed movement of particles, able to enter the Earth's internal magma, and even into the interior of the star.

4. Derivation of the principle of electromagnetic force from the Viewing Angle Principle

The Viewing Angle Principle has the greatest universality, including gravitational and antigravitational forces, and the principles of all fundamental forces can be obtained by the Viewing Angle Principle. To derive the principle of electromagnetic force, assumptions must be made about the structure and wave shapes of electrons and protons. In the process of assumption, it is necessary to consider the quantum properties of electrons and protons, such as electrodes and spins, and the macroscopic phenomenon of electromagnetic interconversion. With the premise of satisfying these properties at the same time, the difference between the presumed structure and the real structure can be minimized.

4.1 Presumed structure of an electron based on its quantum properties

As in Fig. 4.1: $\overrightarrow{oa\bar{o}}, \overrightarrow{ob\bar{o}}$ are the electric fields of the EM variations, and o', o'' are the closed loops formed by the magnetic fields of the EM variations.

$(\overrightarrow{oa\bar{o}}, o')$ is the up-spinning phase of the electromagnetic wave, in which the \overrightarrow{oa} segment is the process of waveform increasing, the \bar{o} segment is the process of waveform decreasing, the waveform reaches the maximum at the apex a , and the waveform reaches the minimum at the center point o . When the electromagnetic waveform reaches its minimum in the \bar{o} direction, the o' magnetic moment reaches its maximum and the waveform begins to form at \overrightarrow{ob} .

$(\overrightarrow{ob\bar{o}}, o'')$ is the downward rotating phase of the electromagnetic wave, in which the \overrightarrow{ob} segment is the process of waveform increase, the \bar{o} segment is the process of waveform decrease, the waveform reaches the maximum at the apex b , and the waveform reaches the minimum at the center point o . When the electromagnetic waveform reaches its minimum in the \bar{o} direction, the o'' magnetic moment reaches its maximum and the waveform begins to form at \overrightarrow{oa} .

Fig. 4.1

The constant circulation of electromagnetic waves from $(\overrightarrow{oa\bar{o}}, o')$ to $(\overrightarrow{ob\bar{o}}, o'')$ creates the relative space of electrons, in which the electromagnetic waves propagate and together with the relative space form the electrons.

4.2 Speculation on the structure of the proton based on its quantum properties

In the structure of the proton, the electromagnetic wave that exhibits electrodes propagates in the opposite direction to that of the electron, and there also exists an electromagnetic wave that is

electrically neutral to the outside world.

(1) The propagation of electromagnetic waves with electrode properties is shown in Fig. 4.2.1:

Fig. 4.2.1

In the figure: \vec{oa}, \vec{ob} is the electric field of the electromagnetic wave change, o', o'' is the closed loop formed by the magnetic field of the electromagnetic wave change.

(\vec{oa}, o') is the up-spinning phase of the electromagnetic wave, in which the \vec{oa} segment is the process of waveform increasing, the \vec{ao} segment is the process of waveform decreasing, the waveform reaches the maximum at the apex a , and the waveform reaches the minimum at the center point o . When the electromagnetic waveform reaches its minimum in the \vec{ao} direction, the o' magnetic moment reaches its maximum and the waveform begins to form at \vec{ob} .

(\vec{ob}, o'') is the downward rotating phase of the electromagnetic wave, in which the \vec{ob} segment is the process of waveform increase, the \vec{bo} segment is the process of waveform decrease, the waveform reaches the maximum at the apex b , and the waveform reaches the minimum at the center point o . When the electromagnetic waveform reaches its minimum in the \vec{bo} direction, the o'' magnetic moment reaches its maximum and the waveform begins to form at \vec{oa} .

Electromagnetic waves showing an electrodynamic character cycle continuously from (\vec{oa}, o') to (\vec{ob}, o'') .

Of the total energy that makes up a proton, the number of electromagnetic waves that exhibit electrodes is much smaller than those that exhibit electroneutrality.

(2) The propagation of an electromagnetic wave that is electrically neutral is shown in Figure 4.2.2:

Electromagnetic waves presenting electrodes and electromagnetic waves presenting electroneutrality together form the relative space of the proton, and all the electromagnetic waves propagate in the relative space and together with the relative space form the proton.

Fig. 4.2.2

(3) Combining the structure of electron and the structure of proton, we can know that before the neutron decays into electron + proton, the structure and waveform of all the electromagnetic waves are shown in Fig. 4.2.2. The process of the neutron decaying into electron + proton is a

process in which part of the electrically charge electromagnetic wave is thrown off to form electron, and another part of the electrically charge electromagnetic wave forms proton together with electro-neutral electromagnetic wave.

4.3 Polarity and repulsion/attraction of electrons/protons

(1) The structural shape of the electron creates the direction of the energy viewing angle, energy viewing angle structure to the outside world as shown in Figure 4.3.1.

Figure 4.3.2: the relative space of electron A, it at B, formed relative to the electron B viewing angle effect; electron B electromagnetic wave in the process of propagation, relative to the "electron A viewing angle structure and direction" formed away from the A energy trend (energy difference) This energy tendency (energy difference) forms the repulsive (--) homopolar electric field force. The result of viewing angle switching is unchanged.

(2) The structural shape of the proton creates the direction of the energy viewing angle, energy viewing angle structure to the outside world as shown in Figure 4.3.3.

Figure 4.3.4: the relative space of proton A, which is at B, formed relative to the role of the viewing angle of the proton B; proton B's electromagnetic wave in the propagation process, relative to the "structure and direction of the viewing angle of the proton A" formed away from the A energy tendency (energy difference), this energy tendency (energy difference) to form the repulsion of the (++) homopolar electric field force. The result of viewing angle switching is unchanged.

(3) As in Fig. 4.3.5. relative space of proton A, which forms a viewing angle action at B; Electromagnetic wave of electron B in the process of propagation, relative to the "viewing angle structure and direction of proton A" formed close to the energy trend of A, this energy trend formed the attraction (+-) anisotropy electric field force. The result of perspective switching is unchanged.

4.4 Viewing angle structure of magnetic poles, and homopolar repulsion and anisotropic attraction of magnetic poles

As shown in Figure 4.4.1, magnetic pole A forms a viewing angle and viewing angle structure to the external space.

As in Figure 4.4.2: the relative space of magnetic pole A forms a viewing angle action at B; magnetic pole B and magnetic pole A are of the same polarity, and the electromagnetic wave of magnetic pole B forms an energy tendency to move away from each other during propagation with respect to the viewing angle action of magnetic pole A, and this energy tendency forms a magnetic force that repels the magnetic poles with the same polarity.

As in Figure 4.4.3: the relative space of magnetic pole A forms a viewing angle action at B; magnetic pole B and magnetic pole A for the opposite polarity, magnetic pole B electromagnetic waves in the propagation process, relative to the role of magnetic pole A's viewing angle to form a mutual tendency to converge the energy trend, this trend of energy to form the magnetic field force of attraction between the opposite magnetic poles.

Fig. 4.4.3

4.5 The Viewing Angle Principle of the electromagnetic force

Electromagnetic force is generated due to the viewing angle interaction of electromagnetic waves in particles participating in electric field force/magnetic field force in a certain direction, and its magnitude depends on the degree of imbalance of viewing angle, viewing angle structure and viewing angle density of electromagnetic waves presenting electrodes (magnetism) in one particle with respect to the degree of imbalance of electromagnetic waves presenting electrodes (magnetism) in the other particle in terms of viewing angle structure and viewing angle density.

The formation of electromagnetic forces requires only the objective existence of viewing angle and perspective structure of electromagnetic forces, and formation of viewing angle interaction, without photon transmission, without any particle, imaginary particle, any medium transmission.

Electromagnetic waves that do not participate in the electric and magnetic field forces are not included in the viewing angle of the electromagnetic force and do not affect the description of the electromagnetic force.

One point of concern: even if the real structure of a particle is vastly different from the schematic diagram, if it exhibits electrodes and magnetism externally, then the electric interaction force, the magnetic interaction force, and the electromagnetic interaction force must follow the viewing angle principle. This also includes the gravitational force, as do the strong and weak forces described later.

Corollary 6: Like the concept of gravitational field, the concepts of electric field, magnetic field and electromagnetic field are also imprecise; they are only one of the external spatial manifestations of the electromagnetic force, and the "field" should be replaced by the concepts of viewing angle and viewing angle structure (or relative spatial action).

4.6 Up-spin and down-spin of Particles

According to the schematic figure 4.3.1 and figure 4.3.3, at any moment, a particle can present an up-spin or down-spin state.

As shown in Fig. 4.6.1 and Fig. 4.6.2, there is a process in which the up-spin and down-spin states are transformed into each other, and if a particle is in the up-spin state at one moment, it is in the down-spin state at the next moment.

The up-spin and down-spin states of a particle interact and balance each other macroscopically, with half of the particles showing up-spin and half showing down-spin when multiple particles are measured.

Between the up-spin and down-spin states, there is a moment of "disappearance".

5. The Viewing Angle Principle of Strong Forces

The principle of generation of strong interaction forces is consistent with gravitational and electromagnetic forces.

Analyzing the strong interaction force in terms of viewing angle, viewing angle structure, and viewing angle density, it is necessary to satisfy, firstly, the asymptotic freedom, and it is not possible to have a situation in which the closer the force acts, the smaller the force, if it is only a general viewing angle. Secondly, it is also necessary to satisfy that larger nuclei have unstable properties. Thirdly, viewing the proton/neutron as prime point cannot describe the viewing angle structure.

Based on these characteristics, it is inferred that there is only one viewing angle that satisfies the basic characteristics of the strong force, as in Figure 5.1:

In the electromagnetic wave propagating in the up-spin phase of proton A, a' is a varying electric field and o' is a varying magnetic field;

In the electromagnetic wave propagating in the down-spin phase of proton B, b' is a varying electric field and o'' is a varying magnetic field.

As in Figure 5.2, the "up-spin stage" of proton A forms a close bond with the "down-spin stage" of proton B.

In the viewpoint of A:

All the electromagnetic waves of A form an energy direction such as a' , o' direction. And the direction of energy as a' , o' form "the viewing angle, viewing angle direction and viewing angle structure of A in the up-spin stage". All the electromagnetic waves b' , o'' of B form an energy

tendency (energy difference) close to each other with respect to "the viewing angle, viewing angle direction and viewing angle structure of A in the up-spin stage".

In the viewpoint of B:

All the electromagnetic waves of B form an energy direction such as b', o'' direction. And the direction of energy as b', o'' form "the viewing angle, viewing angle direction and viewing angle structure of B in the down-spin stage". All the electromagnetic waves a', o' of A form an energy tendency (energy difference) close to each other with respect to "the viewing angle, viewing angle direction and viewing angle structure of B in the down-spin stage".

Then, by the interaction of energy tendency (energy difference) between up-spin stage of A and down-spin stage of B, the strong interaction force between protons A, B is formed.

This strong force model satisfies all the characteristics of the strong interaction force, including asymptotic freedom, short-range action, etc.

As in Fig. 5.3: it can be predicted that within $1/2$ particle radius, when the distance between particles is less than $d2$ tends to $d1$, the tighter the binding, the smaller the action of the strong force (as shown in $d1$);

When the bond is not tight, the viewing angle action becomes larger and the effect of the force becomes larger (as shown in $d2$);

When the distance is greater than $d3$, out of the combination of particles away from the range, then away from the viewing angle action range of the strong force, the role of the strong force is rapidly reduced to 0, and by the electromagnetic force (as shown in $d3$).

Fig. 5.3

The strong interaction force is generated by two particles due to the difference in their mutual viewing angle, and its magnitude depends on the viewing angle structure and viewing angle density of the particles, and it does not require the transfer of any particles, imaginary particles, or any medium.

6. The Viewing Angle Principle of Weak Forces

The weak interaction force also arises due to the energy tendency (energy difference) that occurs between particles, it following the Viewing Angle Principle.

According to the characteristics of the decay of atomic nuclei, it can be deduced from the principles of gravity and antigravity that the nature of the weak interaction force is the same as that of the strong force, because the direction of view of the weak force forms an angle of 90° with the structure of the strong force, and some of the fluctuations propagating in this direction form an "antigravity" effect, which leads to the appearance of decay. This part of the fluctuation carries some of the particles away from the strong interaction and decays into separate particles and energy. The weak force only partially cancels the strong force.

The phenomenon occurs because of the impact of the particles, or the disturbance of space by

electromagnetic waves in the particles, or other reasons, there are certain contingencies in the nucleus that cause the viewing angle, viewing angle structure, and viewing angle density between the two groups of particles to be deflected by a certain angle. When the angle of deflection is exactly equal to 90° , such a perspective appears between the two groups of particles:

Relative to the viewing angle, viewing angle structure, and viewing angle density of A, the electromagnetic wave of B moves away from the direction of A;

relative to the viewing angle, viewing angle structure, and viewing angle density of B, the electromagnetic waves of A form a direction away from B;

An energy tendency (energy difference) to move away from each other is created between A and B (Figure 6).

The reason why certain radioactive substances have half-lives: there is a certain radioactive isotope in a clump of material, and the particles in the nuclei of all the atoms of that isotope need to satisfy a certain probability so that the viewing angle of the particles satisfies the 90° structure and orientation described above. This probability is fixed and forms a half-life.

Since the viewing angle structure of the weak force is more complex than that of the strong force, Figure 6 is too simple and needs to be plotted with computer simulations.

7. Unified description of fundamental forces

In the foregoing explanations of gravitational, electromagnetic, strong, and weak forces, all of them are generated due to differences in viewing angle, and their magnitude depends on the energy tendency (energy difference) formed by viewing angle, viewing angle structures, and viewing angle densities, and they do not need to be transmitted by any particles, imaginary particles, or any medium.

All the above explanations of the fundamental forces are simple and direct, and are universal in explaining the phenomenon of transmitting forces without contact.

A **unified description of the four fundamental forces** can be deduced on this basis:

The fundamental force is generated by particles because of differences in their mutual viewing angle, the magnitude of which depends on the total amount of waves of a particle involved in the action of this force, relative to the degree of imbalance (energy difference) in the viewing angle, viewing angle structure, and viewing angle density of the other particle in relation to this force. The fundamental force does not require the transmission of any particle, imaginary particle, or any medium.

Gravitational, electromagnetic, strong, and weak forces have different relative viewing angle structures, creating different properties of the force;

Examining the several fundamental forces of action in terms of viewing angle structure allows all truths to be seen.

The guiding idea of deducing the above theory is because the relative space cannot exist separately from the cosmic space, and it can be called the relative space of particles, which is a part of the space circled by all the waves/energy of the particles, and no matter how this relative space is changed, and no matter how huge the energy in the relative space is, it is still a part of the space with respect to the cosmic space to see the phenomena of curvature, distortion, folding, compression, etc., and it is still a part of the cosmic space, then the interactions between particles must follow the rules of Viewing Angle Principle.

Even if more fundamental forces are discovered in the future, if they are within the universe, they can be described within the framework of Viewing Angle Principle.

According to the Viewing Angle Principle, there is no need to translate between relative spaces during the formation of the fundamental forces. Under the Viewing Angle Principle, the "mass-energy increment" of particles due to relative motion has nothing to do with the formation of the fundamental force, and even if the particles are moving close to the speed of light or the speed of light, it will not change the basis of the existence of the fundamental force, and the magnitude and the direction of the fundamental force will not be changed due to the relative motion, so In calculating the fundamental forces, the particles/matter in question all have to be counted in terms of static mass.

In my previous article, author defined electromagnetic waves as spatial change quanta, and from the Viewing Angle theory in this article, it can prove that author definition of spatial change quanta is correct, and spatial change quanta is the interaction of change and blocking, and it is Viewing Angle and consciousness at work. At the same time, this can also prove that author's first article on the relevant theory is also universal.

8. Structure of electrons, protons, real-time super distance entanglement of quanta

8.1 Structure of Extranuclear Electrons

We know that the outermost extra-nuclear electrons between different atoms can form chemical bonds.

While describing the strong force, the authors found that the chemical bond binding force also follows the Viewing Angle Principle and is identical to that of the strong force, and that the description of the chemical bond binding force agrees with the unified description of the fundamental forces. As in Figure 8.1.

The electrons can form chemical bonding bonds with each other by the action of the Viewing Angle, which maximizes the bonding between pairs of electrons and satisfies the asymptotic freedom which makes the bond correspondingly elastic.

The Viewing Angle Principle of the chemical bonding force leads to the way in which the

paired electrons combine outside the nucleus. Pairs of electrons outside the nucleus are dependent on the chemical bonding force for their stable existence. Pairs of electrons are formed at different orbital levels in the form of s orbitals (spherical), p orbitals (spindle), d orbitals, f orbitals (petal) and other shapes, which are the structure of the electrons.

8.2 Wave shapes of atomic nuclei

According to the Viewing Angle Principle of the strong force, the shape of the combination of atomic nuclei can be deduced from the shape of the existence of electrons outside the nucleus. Between each pair of protons (neutrons), pairs of particles to form a strong force of the two hemispheres, combined with each other and in the center of the nucleus, not formed a strong force of the two hemispheres in the other moment at the ends of the multiple pairs of protons also formed a spherical, spindle and petal-shaped structure, which is like the shape of the extra-nuclear pairs of electrons.

Corollary 7: In the same atom, the shape of the nucleus (protons and neutrons) is like that of the electrons outside the nucleus, the electromagnetic waves that make up the electric field force propagate in opposite directions, they form a delicate balance. The shape of the electrons outside the nucleus can also be regarded as the "glow emitted" of the shape of the nucleus. The shape of all the atoms is the "Lotus Flower".

8.3 Quantum entanglement in real time and over distance

A closer look at the structure of electrons and protons reveals a deeper phenomenon:

Taking the proton/electron as an example (Fig. 8.3), the relative space of the proton/electron is not completely isolated from the cosmic space; in the proton's view, a small amount of electromagnetic waves o' emitted perpendicularly from the poles of the proton merges with the cosmic space; in the electron's view, a small amount of electromagnetic waves o' of the cosmic space vertically converge on the electron at the poles of the electron; and in the proton and electron's view, a small amount of electromagnetic waves are emitted from the proton's poles and merge into the cosmos, and at the same time, a small amount of electromagnetic waves emitted from the electron's poles merge into the cosmos. and merge into the universe, while at the same time merging vertically into the electron from the electron's poles; a change at any point in the proton/electron acts simultaneously on cosmic space, and the effect of that change will pervade the entire universe; and a change in cosmic space also acts simultaneously on the proton/electron. Every particle is connected to cosmic space for this reason.

Fig. 8.3

It exists in every particle in the universe, so all quanta will form quantum entanglement for this reason. When pairs of electrons are stripped at the same time, two entangled electrons are formed, and when the state of one of the entangled particles is determined, the other is affected at the same time and an entanglement effect is formed.

This is just the principle of information transfer that enables quanta to form super-distance entanglement. The core principle of forming quantum entanglement is since the universe is a spiritual body, so that the cosmic space from the quantum scale to consciously maintain a state of equilibrium, and this equilibrium will be maintained from the quantum scale to the macroscopic and cosmic scales. If the equilibrium state cannot be maintained, the universe will return to disorder and chaos, forming a super-distance hyper-speed spiral and distorting the entire cosmic space.

The special form in which particle's relative space can be connected to cosmic space, makes it possible for people can communicate with the universe through any particle, all the information of any life is stored in the universe. In the perspective of the universe, every particle is connected to the universe as one. All existence in the universe is attributed to the One. All of this is the work of the Creator, who created and maintains cosmic space, and who is everywhere.

The Viewing Angle Principle can be extended, and God's Viewing Angle can be applied to explain many more phenomena, and can be the basis of a theory that runs through everything. Everything in the universe can be seen as it is from God's Viewing Angle. (Note: In this article, "God" is one of the names of the Creator.)

1) First author: Li Yan (李岩) (ORCID ID:0009-0007-9009-140X)

2) Second author: Li JiaXin(李佳欣) (ORCID ID: 0009-0006-2037-3017) (Note: Discovered the up-spin and down-spin structures of protons and electrons, and details of the strong force)

① Laboratory Test of the Isotropy of Light Propagation at the 10⁻¹⁷ level. Physical Review Letters. 2009. Eisele, Ch.; Netsky, A. Yu.; Schiller, S.

② Resolution 1 of the 17th CGPM. BIPM. 1983 [2009-08-23].

③ New viewpoint in Physics (Gravitation principle And We can made the UFO), Personal Articles at Amazon, ISBN:9781728682389. And in zenodo.org, 10.5281/zenodo.8423688.